

DiverIMPACTS

Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains Towards Sustainability

Deliverable 6.4

Strategy paper for professional training, vocational and higher education on crop diversification

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Work package leader: Katie Bliss, Organic Research Center

Deliverable leader: Rim Baccar, ESA, Aline Vandewalle, CA-PdL APCA

Authors: Rim Baccar, ESA, Aline Vandewalle, CA-PdL APCA, Louis Lebrun, ESA, Timothée Chérière CA-PdL APCA, Raj Chongtham Iman - SLU

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1. Executive Summary

Knowledge and skills gaps have been identified as key barriers to crop diversification. Higher education, professional training and all AKIS actors have a key role to address these gaps. This report aims at: identifying needs to be addressed to accompany crop diversification, developing associated skills and knowledge that should be mastered to fill in gaps, listing examples of resources from DiverIMPACTS activities and formulating some recommendations to adapt the strategy of formal education and professional training development.

In the first part of the deliverable report consisting of a review of needs to be addressed to accompany crop diversification, we identify three major dimensions: (i) understand the dynamics of transition towards crop diversification through the analysis of the mechanisms and the knowledge which underpin the introduction of a new crop at farm level, (ii) address the complexity of systems, the inherent uncertainties related to crop diversification knowledge and their implications for information and advisory systems, (iii) consider the relations between farmers, advisors, teachers and the multi-level socio-technical systems that are driving the crop diversification dynamics.

This structuration brings out key skills, knowledge and attitudes (for teachers, advisors, farmers and actors of value chain) to foster crop diversification, that are developed in the second part. The importance of systemic understanding for action is highlighted, multi-disciplinary and contextualized knowledge is needed to understand the context of the different actors involved in crop diversification and be able to link up different learning processes. Actors' understanding of their systems through different scales (from field to territory scale) is an important way of improving interaction between actors.

Many resources from DiverIMPACTS could be used as training materials to support the development of skills: tools for practical work with students or trainees, practice abstracts, success stories and other inspirational resources as contents for training and education but also for technical watch for actors. Resources from DiverIMPACTS should be helpful to emphasize systemic approach in educational programs and training contents. The ways of animation and information sharing, which have been developed and used with case studies teams, are also inspiring examples for training and education.

Finally, we formulate some practical recommendations to adapt the strategy of formal education and professional training development with the aim to enhance crop diversification along the value chain.

The table below (Table 1) summarizes the different kind of skills and knowledge to master for fostering crop diversification at different scales and describes resources from the project that could be used in training, education but also for personal skills development and technical watch.

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Table 1 Summary of skills and knowledge to master and usable resources from DiverIMPACTS. Skills are represented with a pink background and knowledge with a blue one.

Gaps to fill by training and learning	Type of skills / knowledge to master	Resources from DiverIMPACTS
Skills necessary for the process of introducing a new crop: See the farm as a whole, with a systemic approach	<p>Problem analysis and strategic thinking (i.e., reflexive thinking, general overview, including larger scales)</p> <p>Diagnosis skills</p> <p>Search and contextualise knowledge for action</p>	<p>WP2 process with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case Studies accompaniment, - co-innovation courses (on group facilitation and progress assessment methods) - leader/ monitor team with complementary roles and skills to support CS activities <p>4 training sessions organized in 2021 (mainly remote sessions due to COVID situation) - WP6</p>
Communication skills: Change the paradigm in the learning and accompaniment approach	<p>General communication skills: Listening, summarizing, questioning, conflict resolution, consensus building, compromise building</p> <p>Innovation broker function: Connect the right people together, identify and amplify ideas and knowledge from actors</p>	
Group facilitation skills: Allow actors to get together, share knowledge, point of views and advance toward a common goal	<p>Designing and leading meetings for groups of peers or multi-actors for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> increasing engagement from actors sharing knowledge and experience organising work together 	
Other skills	Skills to adapt machine settings (adapting width, seeding/harvesting settings) or bring variation to existing machinery principles	<p>Report under preparation on machinery lock-ins and solutions (WP5)</p> <p>Practice abstract on machinery (to be delivered)</p>
Knowledge diverse in form and nature: Generate usable knowledge for action by linking fundamental knowledge, technical knowledge and empirical observations of actors (mainly farmers) in a given context	<p>Promote multi-disciplinarity</p> <p>Contextualized knowledge: Link fundamental and technical knowledge</p> <p>Experimentation knowledge: on-farm experimentation, methods and steps of experimentation, networking and exchange on experimentation, on-field observations</p>	<p>Co-innovation courses to promote multi-disciplinary and multi-actor approach with resources for systemic analysis</p> <p>Inspirational documents such as success stories (WP1)</p>
Field and crop specific knowledge: Elementary knowledge on crop diversification (concepts, strategies, features, benefits)	<p>Crop diversification strategies: stress the various diversification options (temporal & spatial) and how to combine them</p> <p>Crop diversification features and benefits: Present and promote crop diversification as a means to overcome problems associated with low diversity cropping systems</p>	<p>Practice Abstracts on diversification strategies</p> <p>Ex-post, ex-ante and upscaling of MCA based on the DiverIMPACTS minimal set of indicators (WP4) and</p>

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	<p>Dynamic process (long-term effects, variable & no immediate effects)</p> <p>Knowledge on pre-crop/carry over effects</p> <p>Move past the rotation concept: Toward a dynamic cropping system planning and adaptive management (crop sequence patterns instead of rotation)</p>	<p>Tools for systemic analysis (SMART at the cropping system scale, MAELIA at the territory scale, LCA protocols at the value chain scale...)</p>
<p>Multi-scale, multi-actor knowledge</p>	<p>Knowledge on crop value chain</p> <p>Impact on management and organisation</p>	<p>Inspirational documents such as success stories (WP1)</p> <p>Method for a fair price for crop diversification (Practice abstract to be published)</p> <p>Existing barriers and key elements of solutions (report under preparation)</p> <p>Elements on Contract design</p>

2. Introduction

Crop diversification is facing many socio-technical lock-ins that have already been reported in the scientific literature (Meynard et al., 2018). Among possibilities and levers to unlock the socio-technical systems, higher education and professional training have been identified as a key lever; a change of paradigm in professional training and higher education is needed to foster crop diversification. This report aims at:

1. Presenting the needs to be addressed to accompany crop diversification;
2. Developing the associated skills and knowledge that should be mastered to fill in gaps with needs;
3. Providing examples of resources (models and tools, inspirational examples and ways of doing) from DiverIMPACTS activities that are usable for training and education activities;
4. Formulating some recommendations to adapt the strategy of formal education and professional training development with the aim to enhance crop diversification along the value chain.

The methodology used was:

- a review of scientific literature on dynamics of the practice changes;
- an analysis of the first outputs of the DiverIMPACTS project and particularly:
 - ***Deliverable D2.3 - Mid-term CSs' evolutions in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators and D6.3 - Needs for training and advisory as well as for formal education:***

The mid-term assessment (D2.3) of CS presents the indicators used, the activities organised and the strategic evolutions of the 25 CSs of DiverIMPACTS. It emphasizes how different stakeholders, organised in CSs, elaborate collective experiences through multiple activities linked to their local challenges. To what extent these observations can be extended to other innovation facilitators/actors?

Different actors of the Agricultural Knowledge and Information System, (AKIS) systems involved in the creation and the sharing of knowledge (through professional training, higher education and advisory services) have also dealt with their needs to support farmers on crop diversification, from their own experiences (D6.3).

Both deliverables, based on ongoing multi-actor group dynamics for the first, and on the expertise of teachers, advisors and farmers for the second, revealed several converging ideas.

- ***Deliverable D5.1 - Ordered list of lock-ins for CSs and the Mapping of barriers to crop diversification (Morel et al, 2020) realized among DiverIMPACTS case studies, which highlighted a set of skills and knowledge gaps.***

A set of interviews with a selection of key actors identified within and outside the project to understand knowledge use in diversification process and the skills and attitudes that should be

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mastered and adopted by actors in agriculture (Supplementary material 1 and Supplementary material 2)

A set of interviews of Work Package leaders of DiverIMPACTS (from WP1 to WP5 - Supplementary material 3): They contribute to identify skills, attitudes and knowledge to address the described needs through the activities of DiverIMPACTS. It also aimed at identifying the outputs of the project that may be mobilised to adopt these attitudes, learn these skills and share knowledge. Finally, DiverIMPACTS members were asked to make propositions during an annual meeting.

This report focuses on the different actors of the AKIS, which is defined as a system that links people and organisations to promote mutual learning, to generate, share, and utilize agriculture-related technology, knowledge and information. Diverse actors from the private, public and non-profit sectors relating to agriculture may be considered as components of an AKIS system. It may include actors such as farmers, farm workers, agricultural educators, researchers, non-academic experts, public and independent private advisors, supply chain actors, and other actors in the agricultural sector (Knierim et al., 2015).

In this document, “knowledge” is used in its broad sense, encompassing fundamental, technical and empirical knowledge, and when necessary, precisions will be added. “Skill” is used in the sense of “knowing-how”, of ways of doing and “attitude” in a broad sense including attitudes and soft-skills.

Similarly, system refers to any system, regardless of the scale of study (e.g., cropping system, farming system, landscape); particular systems will be mentioned when relevant. Finally, actor has to always be understood as any person involved in farming and related value chains, including amongst others: farmers, advisors, researchers, manufacturers, retailers, teachers. When appropriate, the specific kind of actors considered will be explicitly mentioned.

3. Review of the needs for professional training and higher education to support diversification

Thanks to the inputs of the DiverIMPACTS project and the scientific literature, 3 types of needs for actors to foster crop diversification were identified.

- Understand the dynamic nature of crop diversification, which is addressed through the mechanisms and the knowledge which underpin the introduction of a new crop at farm level.
- Encompass the diversity of knowledge production and of sharing in a context of increasing variability and uncertainty. This increased variability and uncertainty are a result of both socio-economic and agro-environmental factors, including changes in the network of actors, norms, market opportunities and prices, and climate.
- Consider the relations between farmers, advisors, teachers and the multi-level socio-technical systems, which are introduced mainly from the case studies (CSs) experiences which are studied and analysed in the WP2 of the project.

This structuration brings out key needs for actors such as teachers, advisors and farmers to stimulate crop diversification, which are further developed hereafter.

3.1. Understand the dynamics of farming practices changes: key-knowledge, learning processes, trajectories

3.1.1. Introducing a new crop implies a design process at the farm level and beyond

At the cropping system level, the introduction of a new crop is often synonym of systemic changes. Systemic from an agronomic point of view, to consider the effect of its introduction on the cropping system (e.g., pre crop effect, pest and diseases management), but also from the whole farming system point of view, with its effect on the economic, social, organisational aspects (Laurent and al., 2003).

Multiple adjustments are done throughout time, both to produce *ad hoc* agronomic references and to adjust the farming system according to its socio-technical context. This transformation of the farmer's work activity can be analysed as a “**step by step re-design**” (Coquil, 2014) where the farmer can be seen both as the manager of his farm (short time scale) and the designer of his working environment (long time scale). During this continuous and adaptive transition process, farmers act by mobilising new knowledge, new indicators and new stakeholders. **These transition pathways should be seen as trajectories** composed by a series of changes which are built by the use of a **range of sources of information** and the realisation of many **learning processes**. Chantre et al., 2014 and Cristofari et al., 2018 analysed the agroecological transition of farmers by looking at specific agronomic practices (e.g., reduction of pesticide use, conservation agriculture, multi-services cover crops introduction) to understand learning processes that enable farmers to develop practices adapted to their local agroecosystem.

In DiverIMPACTS, similar observations have been made when focusing on cash crop diversification, which often induced modifications and learning processes not only on agronomic aspects but also on

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logistic, work organisation, economic and social aspects of the farming activities. In the study carried out by E. Revoyron (see Deliverable 5.3), 16 interviews were carried out with farmers who diversified their cropping systems in West of France. This study highlighted that farmers bring together multiple knowledge, multiple actors of the socio-economic environment and several rounds of tests at the farm level in order to produce contextualized references necessary for action and to adapt the farm structure to make the introduction of new crops effective. Learning processes described in the activity of crop diversification are mainly characterized by:

- the nature of the object (agronomic, organizational, socio-economic);
- the type of stakeholders mobilized (advisors, peers, groups of peers, economic organisation); and
- the type of test performed (experiments, practice transfer, comparison with neighbours) (see, Lebrun, 2020).

Acting on the **post-production activities** (post-harvest, storage, commercialization ...) and on the imbrication of the farm in its **socio-economic context** (partnerships, involvement in stakeholders' network, ...) to maintain a diversified cropping system was also highlighted. For example, farmers who introduce minor crops and maintain a cropping system with a high level of diversification were directly involved in developing outlets (i.e., downstream of the value chain). They developed on-farm processing activities, local commercialization, and/or elaborated contracts with industrials. These observations are consistent with results of DiverIMPACTS drivers for crop diversification: economic independence, workload, aim for farm autonomy ... (Mérot et al., 2019; Revoyron et al., 2019). The qualitative survey performed within WP1 and analysing crop diversification initiatives across Europe (unrelated to DiverIMPACTS), showed that these initiatives mainly aimed at improving environmental preservation, crop production stability, increasing economic income, or having new food product...

3.1.2. Actionable knowledge are diverse in their nature and form

Diversification mobilizes a holistic approach within and beyond the agroecosystem. The exclusive focus on technological knowledge is insufficient because lock-ins are not purely technological (Meynard et al., 2018). During roundtables performed in Task 6.3, scientists, advisors and farmers pointed out the lack of fundamental knowledge to address **interactions between soil, plants, pests and climate conditions**. All actors expressed the importance to better know the mechanisms underlying potential benefits and risks during the conception and the management of diversified cropping systems in a specific context. The on-going field experiments carried out in WP3 will bring out knowledge which could help understand and assess potential benefits and risks related to diversification. A similar focus is found in CSs activities (WP2). Indeed, 36% of the events organized by CS were devoted to “generating knowledge” (thanks to for instance on-farm trials, surveys, inquiry interviews or reporting of research results). During the same period, among lessons learned, that 42% refer to “specific learning about CS topic” (Deliverable 2.3). Those learning lessons **bring fundamental and technical knowledge together**. Technical knowledge follows on from the fundamental knowledge and the needs for it are mainly expressed by farmers (Deliverable 6.3), in the form of e.g., choice of varieties, sowing densities, or machines settings. Working in group on a specific and contextualised topic (like the CSs of DiverIMPACTS) seems to **be an efficient way to generate technical knowledge**.

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In light of these results, the lack of references on diversification crops and their effects at the rotation and agroecosystem levels are still a huge barrier (Meynard et al., 2018). Simultaneous use and production of fundamental and technical knowledge by farmers as observed in CSs corroborate the work of Toffolini et al. (2017). Farmers articulate several types of knowledge (e.g., fundamental and empirical, contextualised and generic) within their own farm when redesigning their cropping systems, all in a step-by-step design. Farmers combine knowledge diverse in nature and in origin to build “hybrid” references which are effective in their local context (Toffolini et al., 2015). As an example of a cropping practice change, Catalogna (2018) could be used as a tool to visualize change as an addition of different trials organized in time. Catalogna (2018) formalized the concepts of “**Experimental Situation / Experimentation Itinerary**” (Figure 1) as a means to monitor the trajectory of farmers who implement a new cropping practice. The idea is to record all those changes undertaken by the farmer over time and in relation to a given practice (e.g., introduction of a new crop), by drawing a time-scale-like figure. This allows to detect synergies between individual and collective dynamics as well as the technical problems faced throughout from the field up to the market.

Figure 1. example of an Experimentation Itinerary which highlight the few Experimental Situations realised during 8 years by a farmer who was introducing cover crops (based on Catalogna, 2018)

3.1.3. Structural barriers and challenges to unlock diversification

At the field scale, stakeholders from roundtables of Task 6.3 pointed out the lack of fundamental knowledge about the soil-plant-organism interactions. Also, farmers insisted on the lack of **technical references to help the agroecosystem management** in order to stimulate these interactions, even when the fundamental knowledge is known. They asked for local references on varieties, sowing densities (especially for intercrops), machinery settings, appropriate soil tillage; often before introducing a new crop.

Ideal-types of food system innovation setting

Changing from within

Conventional farming practices promoting longer rotations (temporal diversification), big farms, long commodity value chains with many large-scale agroindustrial and retailing intermediaries.

Example of DiverIMPACTS case studies close to ideal-types

CS 19, SE:

The CS involves various stakeholders (in the value chain and in the society) to promote grain legume production. It will lead to develop local food systems and strengthen the links between various societal actors.

Building outside

Organic farming practices integrating minor crops and intercropping, small farms, short local value chains involving a limited number of small-scale downstream actors.

CS 23, NL:

Vegetable growers share progress and possible solutions to better manage their workload in order to better maintain a high number of crops through improved marketing and/or farm management.

Playing horizontal

Crop diversification supported by territorial arrangements between arable and livestock farmers and/or spatial diversification without harvested intercrops. No change in downstream value chains.

CS 11, FR:

The case study contributes to design diversified crop systems with a multi-actor approach, and to develop the feed exchanges between farmers in the area.

Figure 2 ideal-types of food systems innovation setting (based on Morel et al., 2020). “F”: farmer”; “I”: intermediary actor of value chain (collector, processor, trader, retailer); “C”: consumer. Arrows represent the flows of products from production to consumption along the value chain. The size of value chain actors is in line with the average size of actors in the different ideal-types, which tended to be smaller in local and organic value chains

At the farm scale and through a transversal analysis of barriers encountered in the CSs, Morel et al. (2020, Figure 2) have analysed the **links between barriers and ideal-types of food system innovation settings**: *changing from within*, *building outside* and *playing horizontal*. This should help narrow down the issue and address fewer barriers. The lack of coordination between producers is still a major issue

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for farms included in long commodity value chain (*Changing from within*), because there is a power unbalance between farmers and agroindustry or retailers. In the *Building outside* category, there is often a lack of coordination between small farms. They need to build short local value chains, design suitable contracts to collaborate efficiently on e.g., logistic, post-harvest, processing. For small farms (in *Building outside* and *Playing horizontal*) which integrate minor crops, the post-harvest management is often a real challenge (it can be the case for big farms also), but not always anticipated, explaining many failures (Lebrun, 2020). Morel et al. (2020) also pointed out the belief that change should come from upstream agroindustry (phytosanitary and machinery).

The scientific literature along with results from different outputs of the DiverIMPACTS project allows to summarize the main needs of farmers and advisors to foster crop diversification (Box 1).

Summary of needs:

- Understand and present the farm as an evolutive structure:
 - Draw a trajectory where the farmer is both the designer and the pilot (different time scales); and
 - See the evolutions of farming practices and the dynamics of farmers groups as trajectories.
- Generate usable knowledge for action by linking fundamental and technical knowledge and empirical observations of actors (mainly farmers) in a given context.
- Consider the farm with a systemic approach:
 - Use a holistic approach of the farm and its socio-economic context; and
 - Realise diagnoses (agronomic, economic, environmental, social, workload, market, ...) in order to identify what could be the expected performances and principal risks and barriers to the introduction of new crops at the farm level (from technical references to post production activities) and beyond (socio-technical context).

Box 1 Summary of needs of farmers and advisors to foster crop diversification

3.2. Apprehend, manipulate and spread diverse, uncertain and incomplete knowledge

3.2.1. Complex systems of knowledge production and sharing

Diversification is facing a difficult paradox: there is a need to spread a lot of knowledge and references (e.g., on minor crops, benefits of diversification) to the largest possible number of actors while this knowledge is not complete, under development or not yet available (Meynard et al., 2013).

Knierim and al. (2015) after having analysed the AKIS systems of all the European countries, concluded that fundamental knowledge produced by universities and research institutes was hardly transmitted to other stakeholders to produce practical knowledge. **Cooperation** between AKIS's organisations is key to exchange information on innovated practices and crops, by mixing the bottom-up and the top-down approach (Elzen et al., 2011). Knierim and al. (2015) recommend to strengthen public infrastructures which have a role of platform to stimulate mutual learning. Rural multi-actor networks should also be developed, especially in countries where the AKIS is fragmented and “weak”. Farm workers, often forgotten, should also be considered and invited at training sessions.

Figure 3 the Triggering Change Model (from Sutherland and al, 2012)

The Triggering Change Model developed by Sutherland and al. (2012) (Figure 3), based on social psychology, is a good representation of the trajectory of many of those farmers involved in a diversification process. It allows to conceptualize how a farmer integrate and build his own “micro-AKIS”, through a stepwise approach. By using this model, AgriLink H2020 (Sutherland and al., 2018) is demonstrating that advisors can play a role at any stage. They may especially be part of the “trigger event”, making farmer aware of particular activities or issues (Sutherland and al., 2018).

3.2.2. Different personal interactions are complementary to advice systems

Use of peer-to-peer networks is growing. Studies led within the H2020 program AgriLink point out the role of geographical proximity and the importance of specific relations in the process of information and knowledge transfer. In these cases, the knowledge transfer is partly shaped by local norms and rules (Sutherland et al., 2018). Several **farmer networks** forms and scales can be distinguished, from a neighbour cooperation to an agricultural professional magazine where situated explorations are made available to readers by narrative methods. There are also **multi-actor networks** which link researchers to farmers, advisors and engineers by focusing on a strategic issue; this type of network

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can be deployed at national (e.g., the DEPHY network in France) or international (e.g., DiverIMPACTS CSs) scale. These **networks appear as complementary** to advisory services, they are an opportunity to connect farmers and advisors with other stakeholders of the value chain. Also, the existence of advisor's networks (Omon et al., 2019), help a real-time adjustment of advisor's activities to new working requirements and contexts.

Chantre et al. (2014) demonstrated that farmers whose trajectory allowed an efficient cropping system redesign are the ones who got information from **different sources and through various channels**, involving various forms of experience and resource persons. Thanks to interviews led in DiverIMPACTS (WP5, D5.3), the same conclusions were drawn for diversification. Farmers implement individual and collective learning processes based on heterogeneous indicators and knowledge coming from a large panel of organisations and stakeholders. Surveys carried out in 15 countries in WP1 of DiverIMPACTS (*Typology of diversification experiences with description of driving factors to support crop diversification, D1.1-D1.2*), showed that the main enablers identified during diversification initiatives were linked to personal interactions, followed by agronomic and economic drivers: "people are the most important success factors" (WP1 highlights, 3rd Annual Meeting, 2019). In the same study, it was observed that the commitment of the involved actors is the factor which contributes the most to diversification initiative successes.

In D6.3, teachers insisted on the need of interactions with other organisations (outside of universities and research institutes) **to cross scales and sectors and combine analytic and empirical knowledge** on case studies.

3.2.3. Change of paradigm in the learning and accompaniment approach

The agroecological paradigm along with the new agricultural networks (enabled thanks to the Internet) are challenging the many stakeholders from advisers to teachers. Stakeholders must integrate the notion of risk, the uncertainty of the result, the continuous evolution of knowledge and the need of a multidisciplinary approach applied to a local context. During the roundtables of Task 3 in WP6, teachers as well as advisors pointed out the need to change from a prescriptive approach to a **coaching/accompaniment approach** (e.g., advisors and teachers become coaches, animators, facilitators rather than prescribers). However, can these new attitudes be adopted? Both advisors and teachers asked for training courses about new pedagogies with the purpose of developing new approaches to interact with farmers and groups of farmers or with learners/students.

Because crop diversification means dealing with uncertain and incomplete knowledge, prescriptive advice is not effective anymore. A good advisor is not the best technical expert of the new crop or practice to be introduced, but should be competent in identifying the on-going dynamics of reference building for a farmer, and understand how the farmer articulates his reflexion with his own practices (Toffolini et al., 2015). This means switching from a prescriptive to a **comprehensive approach**. The role of advisors and teachers then will be to help the contextualisation processes in order to support the elaboration of local practice references. This consists in **linking the lived experience** by a farmer with observations done during the action, experience of other farmers or actors, and new knowledge about the processes of the issue. This work cannot be based only on the technical-economic context of the farm but mainly on the farmer's diversification trajectory.

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Due to public policy evolutions and to variety of sector organisations across countries, the advice professions are diverse and changing in term of activities, attitudes and localisation in the AKIS (Kielbasa et al., 2015; Labarthe et al., 2013; Labarthe and Laurent, 2013). For example, commercial services are implemented in the activities of public organisation, transforming the relationships between farmers and advisors (Compagnone et al., 2013). On the one hand, the advisor can hardly keep a prescriptive attitude on most of the diversification crops. On the other hand, he/she has a key role in coordinating information from all AKIS organisations. Labarthe and al. (2013) showed that the time spent in R&D activities become a negligible part of the advisor's work, especially for private advice. However, back-office activities are brought to be more based on peer **networks and platforms** (e.g., Dephy network in France (Cerf et al., 2017)).

3.2.4. Need of tools and methods to help diagnostics and evaluations

In the meantime, advisors ask for **holistic decision-support tools and design-aid tools**. It may help them see farm as a whole and switch from one scale to another. They see the incorporation of scientific knowledge in numeric tools as a means to reassuring themselves in complex situations when they don't have the expertise on a specific crop or practice, or even on a niche market (D6.3). Advisors also express their motivation to spend time to be trained in the use of such kind of tools. The **toolbox** currently developed in Task6.2/WP6 (<https://www.diverimpacts.net/toolbox>) matches with this need to guide users to choose the appropriate tools according to their specific environment, their marketing strategy, and the farm profile.

By *tool*, we understand three types of objects, methods, or numeric tools potentially used by advisors, farmers but also teachers in their pedagogic activities. We distinguish three types of tools, differing in the purpose of their implementation:

- Multicriteria assessment (ex: Systerre®, SMART-Farm, ...)
- Decision support tools (ex: method to adjust fertilisation, suggest intercrop species, ...)
- Design aid (ex: SEGAE - (Jouan et al., 2020); GASCON - (Aubertot et al., 2018))

Many tools can be used around crop diversification. Among all these possibilities, farmers and advisors cannot develop expertise for all but they should be able to choose the relevant tool for a given issue, a given context, and at the strategic time. The skills previously presented could equip actors to choose the right tool for the right context and put tool outputs within the farmer's reflexion process.

The scientific literature and d outputs of DiverIMPACTS allowed to summarize the main needs of farmers and advisors to manipulate and share uncertain and diverse knowledge usable for diversification (Box 2).

Summary of needs:

- Be aware of its own position in a complex system of knowledge production and diffusion (partial knowledge or under construction):
 - adapt its own attitude to the situation and context; and
 - be able to address a problem appealing to different disciplines: agronomy, ecology, economy, sociology, management, even marketing or industrial processing.
- Choose the relevant information channels, tools and methods according to the problematic context:
 - mobilise and cross different sources of information;
 - use experience platform or network as source of knowledge; and
 - identify the relevant tools according to the context.
- For advisors and teachers, adopt an attitude of enabler, facilitator:
 - have an accompaniment approach;
 - have a comprehensive approach; and
 - put students and farmers in a reflexive attitude (collectively and individually) about the knowledge they already have and the scales they are manipulating.

Box 2 Summary of needs of farmers and advisors to manipulate and share uncertain and diverse knowledge usable for diversification

3.3. Impulse transition in a sociotechnical context

3.3.1. Connect stakeholders to share information and coordinate actions

One main conclusion of T6.3 roundtables in WP6 is that exchanges and meetings on the topic of diversification between different actors are currently missing, even though all actors were already somehow interconnected through their activities. Although the need of peer exchange come as a necessity in several studies on agroecology practices (Chantre et al., 2014; Coquil, 2014), the demand arises once again from farmers and advisors. Exchanges between different actors are emphasized by farmers, advisors and teachers as a way to bringing out ideas and comprehend the uncertain effects of diversification practices such as the introduction of a new crop. As an illustration of this need, almost all CSs of the DiverIMPACTS project were involved in the **scaling practice of creating multi-actor dialogues**. In fact, they spent a huge part of their activities on organizing public presentations, field/farm open days, workshops, publishing articles, study trips and professional days. Those events had several goals and results: animate partnerships, broaden a network, promote certain models, or disseminate knowledge about research results and practical tips. We can also notice that almost all

the CSs have established partnerships and created alliances through different forms (Deliverable 2.3). Some forms of partnerships can be based on or be inspired by the existing local inter-farm cooperation (Lucas et al., 2019) based on the geographical proximity of few actors. By sharing farm equipment, they also have informal interactions and share information at the local scale. Studies about the diversification of farming activities (not necessarily linked to crop diversification) show that many farmers build new forms of peer-collaborations and local partnerships in opposition to the dominant long value chains (Morel et al., 2020). In DiverIMPACTS' CSs, actors try to initiate different types of partnerships. These partnerships took different forms. They can be established between different actors or organisations: with additional farmers, with research programs, with seed and inputs companies, with material producers, with advice organizations and downstream value chain companies or organisations. According to the expected results by CSs actors, these partnerships elaborated collaborations on a large diversity of topics: acquire agronomic references, disseminate knowledge, develop new farming practices, develop new market or even carry out political lobbying. These partnerships can be presented as a lever to impact the socio-technical regime and facilitate the coordination of stakeholders along the value chains. In the CSs of DiverIMPACTS, activities like face-to-face meetings, professional days or study trips seem to impulse and stimulate partnerships.

3.3.2. Networks and multi-stakeholder groups to act in a local context

Many authors consider that agroecological issues have to be seen as “wicked problems” (Steyaert et al., 2016; Urmetzer et al., 2020). Wicked because their causes are emergent and complex and their effects are uncertain. That is why it is difficult to solve them. Address problems linked to diversification without considering other actors is futile because locks-in are sociotechnical by nature (Meynard and al., 2018). To manage these complex sociotechnical transitions, Steyart and al. (2016) propose the concept of **intermediation**. **Intermediation can be defined as confronting the different interpretative perceptions of stakeholders, constructed on a same reality, and highlight the power relationships (economic, logistic, social, politic, cultural) in order to understand how heterogeneous people make sense of a shared reality and to create new socio-technical configurations** (Jollivet, 2020; Steyaert et al., 2016). By their activity of networking, the intermediary workers (e.g., advisors) organized the sharing of individual experiences. According to Elzen et al., 2011, favour **reflexive learning** relies on a cooperation between all stakeholders and special attention paid to the effects of framing actor positions (practices, processes, ethical). Urmetzer and al. (2020) explored few higher education programs of bioeconomy across Europe in order to analyse how academic education can equip future workers to act within these “wicked problems”. They reveal that an important place is attributed to the development of skills to **effectively communicate with diverse audiences**. Modules are dedicated to how to support the participation of multiple stakeholders on a concrete problem. They insist on the identification of relevant stakeholders and the analysis of their involvement to better understand the multitude of roles and perceptions of each stakeholder. **This kind of activities can develop skills for intermediation**. Also, student personal experiences are mobilised and relies on scholar activities, to enable a reflexive learning.

DiverIMPACTS - Deliverable 6.4

By studying two alternative agricultural networks, Coquil and al. (2019) proposed models of networks based on peer exchanges based on strong multi-actor interactions by partnerships with research institutes. They point out the role of animators and the necessity for farmers to **be involved in the strategic** and political objectives of their local group to make the intermediation effective. Re-thinking ethical values and the governance of the group is necessary to move from single to multiple learning (Pahl-Wostl, 2009). Similar dynamics is observed in DiverIMPACTS case studies: 39% of their events are classified as “action plan development” (Deliverable 2.3). They were devoted to the exploration of intervention options; identify case study entry points and next intervention steps. Through those events, CSs participants set up missions, strategy and governance of the group and they were able to **choose the CS directions** for next months. These observations can be linked to studies on the communities of practice formed by farmers (Dolinska and d’Aquino, 2016). Farmers are seen as agents in innovation systems, when they construct knowledge collectively by opening space for negotiation of meanings and evaluation of innovation projects.

We can also consider the work satisfaction and the positive emotion that emerge from the changing farming practices performed through cooperation and relationships with stakeholders (Barbier et al., 2015). It is difficult to estimate those elements but they are important to capture with some **social indicators** (workload is not sufficient) and to consider the work as an important factor of the systems approach (Coquil et al., 2018) (Deliverable 4.1). In order to develop a systems approach, Coquil et al. (2018) propose to consider the farmer work as a relation between the farmer and his natural and social environment (Bueguin, 2007).

3.3.3. Approaches to scaling up and out the changes

As we saw previously, sociotechnical changes needed to diversify European cropping systems can be conceptualised using the multi-level perspective of Geels (2002) (Figure 4).

DiverIMPACTS - Deliverable 6.4

Increasing structuration of activities in local practices

Figure 4 a multi-level perspective framework on system innovation (Geels, 2002)

Studies performed within the AgriLink H2020 program suggested to consider the multi-level perspective framework as a base to build transition pathway of advisory systems. In Deliverable 2.3 of DiverIMPACTS, CSs trajectories were analysed by using the framework created by Wigboldus and Leeuwis (2013) (Figure 5). They delineated approaches to *scaling up* and *scaling out* in agricultural development

In our context, the terms “scaling out” and “scaling up” correspond to (Figure 5):

Scaling out: a multiplication, a replication, an expansion, a dissemination at the same scale or towards different scale level of a process, a technology, a concept, an organization.

Scaling up: a transition, an institutionalisation, a transformation, an integration, an incorporation involving a complexification of a process, a technology, a concept, an organization.

DiverIMPACTS - Deliverable 6.4

Figure 5 difference between scaling up and scaling out (from Wigboldus and Leeuwis, 2013)

Both scaling approaches can be understood as ways to achieve a desired impact. We propose to use it to understand which scaling strategy is on-going in a group of farmers working on diversification. Scaling approaches are relevant to conceptualise how a diversification initiative can be developed, shared and transferred across the multi-level perspective framework (typically from the technological niche to the sociotechnical regime).

Deliverable 2.3 demonstrated that it is possible to identify which approach is on-going in a given CS by looking at the activities organized, the goals and mission defined.

The different approaches are defined as such (Figure 6):

Figure 6 general approaches to scaling up and out (from Wigboldus and Leeuwis, 2013)

DiverIMPACTS - Deliverable 6.4

Push “We have something that we would like to go to scale and we will work hard to make that happen.”

Pull “We have an aspired future in mind and seek to scale up and out that which we think will help make that future reality.”

Plant “We have something we would like to go to scale, but such *scaling* can only happen if we connect other factors and work with other actors.”

Probe “We have an aspired future in mind, but are unsure about what *scaling* processes would be involved in moving towards that future, so we will have to navigate and adapt as we go.”

By analysing the Learning History of each CS, the type of approach of each CS has been identified. No clear relations between the CS approach to *scaling* (Push/Pull/Plant/Probe) and the type of event organised by the CS were really identified, but they revealed different descriptions of the same activities. For example, there were field trials, meetings or workshops across all approaches, but these instruments were used in different ways, with different goals. So, we notice that the same means can be used for different approaches. It is also important to know that CSs can move from one approach to another, for example: CS13 moved from plant to push starting an open exploration to the opportunities for diversification in the Champagne region. The interest from parties working on methanization, made them move in this direction, and they started to work on the implementation of methanization plants and of the cropping systems feeding these plants (D2.3).

To better analyse the *scaling* of innovation, the concept of *anchoring* has been developed by Elzen et al. (2012). It is defined as “the process in which a **novelty becomes newly connected**, connected in a new way, or connected more firmly to a niche or a regime. The further the process of anchoring progresses, meaning that more new connections supporting the novelty develop, the larger the chances are that anchoring will eventually develop into durable links.” (Elzen et al. 2012). The anchoring can be done by three ways: **technological, network and institutional**. Connections which support the novelty development can be done or fostered by advisors, animators and even teachers when they are involved in the group dynamic as they are in some DiverIMPACTS case studies.

Concepts of *scaling* and *anchoring* could be good tools to establish a diagnostic of the dynamic of a farmer group, and even a farmer who is introducing a new crop. **By detecting what approach is deployed by the group, an advisor can select the usable competences and activities which could be set up in order to assist the group progression and trajectory.** For that, we need to associate, for each type of approach to scaling, the competences needed and the appropriate attitudes.

The scientific literature and different outputs of DiverIMPACTS allows to summarize the main needs faced by farmers and advisors to impulse transition in a sociotechnical environment.

Summary of needs:

- Be able to create multi-actor dialogues:
 - understand the roles and the perceptions of each stakeholder (stakeholders can be actors present all along the supply chain);
 - communicate with diverse audiences; and
 - identify who are the key/ relevant stakeholders for each “activity” (to mobilise, to get references, to integrate work groups, to elaborate partnerships).

- See the evolutions of farming practices and the dynamics of farmers groups as trajectories, composed and built by regular rethinking of the goals, missions, strategy and places of stakeholders:
 - be able to formalize the learning achieved, to create reflexivity on realised activities and adjust the upcoming strategies; and
 - build the group or farm strategic orientation according to the sociotechnical environment evolutions.

- Be able to characterise a diversification initiative:
 - detect what scaling approach and what type of anchoring is deploying; and
 - bring specific tools, knowledge or stakeholders to foster the dynamic

Box 3 summary of needs of farmers and advisors to impulse transition in a sociotechnical environment

3.4. Conclusion

To meet these three levels of needs:

- To understand the dynamics of farming practices changes;
- To apprehend, manipulate and spread diverse uncertain and incomplete change; and
- To impulse transition in a sociotechnical context,

actors should master new skills, attitudes and knowledge which are diverse and may be combined.

Figure 7 aims at considering the different interactions between actors and knowledge, skills and attitudes involved. This representation should be also, for each country, adapted to its AKIS properties. Therefore, knowledge and information circulate within the different actors in an AKIS system. AKIS systems differ widely in their organisation and complexity depending on the European country (Knierim and Prager, 2015). To allow a better understanding of who produces and exchanges agricultural knowledge and help identify any gaps or missing links, we can refer to the different diagrams produced in the pro-AKIS project (<http://www.proakis.eu/> Dec. -12 to May -15).

Figure 7 synthetic representation of the needs to support crop diversification through professional training and higher education

*“advisors”, involves a large panel of workers. To better understand the diversity of situations and workers considered, we propose to use the typology elaborated in the AgriLink H2020 program by applying the concept of knowledge intense business services (KIBS). This typology is relevant to understand how the different services interact with each other and with other AKIS actors (e.g., farmers, teachers, researchers). In Europe, institutions and businesses that are involved in advisory provision can be classified as (Sutherland and al., 2018):

- Type 1: independent consultant who sell advice;
- Type 2: client-owned advisory organisations;
- Type 3: embedded advisory organisations, where services come together with another commercial activity for the farm (e.g., seeds, inputs);
- Type 4: public or semi-public KIBS;
- Type 5: NGO not controlled by farmers.

4. From needs to skills, attitudes and knowledge: highlights from DiverIMPACTS

The first part of this report was dedicated to a review of needs, presented with three complementary approaches (dynamics of changes, diverse and uncertain knowledge to apprehend and share,

transition in global sociotechnical context). In this part, needs are translated into skills, attitudes and knowledge that actors should master. Most of them are transversal to these three approaches. We focus on those that were mainly highlighted in DiverIMPACTS activities, based on WP leaders interviews and deliverable contents (from WP1 to WP6).

4.1. Skills actors should master

4.1.1. Skills necessary for the process of introducing a new crop

Some general skills have been put forward during the interviews performed with DiverIMPACTS WP leaders. Amongst them, skills related to **problem analysis and strategic thinking**, such as reflexive thinking, ability to take a step back and understand the problem from different points of view, including the relevance of a project in a larger scale context (e.g., territory, country). Critical analyses of the situation and its context is the first step before taking any decision and action. Nonetheless, during the analysis the actors have to keep in mind their objectives to identify possible strategies to generate change and obtain desired results. This process could be summarized as **action-oriented analysis skills**.

Analysis and diagnostic skills are also important to understand the reasons for crop failure, when it happens, as farmers tend to abandon a diversification crop when they do not understand the reasons for its failure. Skills to link fundamental knowledge to technical and empirical ones has been mentioned by an actor involved in DiverIMPACTS to help identify relevant diagnostic and understanding of the success and failure of crop diversification and to contextualise knowledge for action.

An actor involved in DiverIMPACTS said about the introduction of a new crop *“Field inspections made a big contribution there, because they showed how to effectively perform one. As a result, beet fields were everywhere. The advice accompanied the cultivation with regular publications. It looked there, what was written in the typical regions and has then published in Emsland.”*

When decision to introduce a new crop in a cropping system has been made, comes the time for actions. The start-up period of a new crop is crucial. Actors must be aware that it often takes several years, and experiences to familiarise with a crop in a given context. Introducing a new crop within a region requires the adaptation or the creation of new references through a process of trial-error-adaptation. **Skills to research identify and adapt relevant references and knowledge to local context** are necessary for farmers and their advisors. They have to be complemented with **experimentation skills**, to set up, if necessary, on-farm experiments and experiment networks to improve contextualised technical knowledge on new crop management. **Working in networks** and the setup of demonstration fields for information sharing may also be very useful.

For value chain organisation, actors must be aware that there could be low and irregular volumes produced during the first years of a new crop introduction. Also, having the right skills to manage variability, accompany farmers in diagnostic and analysis, reference creation and adaptation, and develop new use and valorisation channels for these newly introduced crop(s) is recommended.

Also, all actors should at least have **basic skills for information search, be aware of the existing knowledge resources and where and how to find necessary knowledge** for their project. They also need to be able to critically assess the quality of information which they encounter/come across.

Actors' **awareness of their position and role in the system and their knowledge of the possible impacts of their choices on other levels of the system** is important to foster group work and take favourable actions by the various actors. Furthermore, self-assessment of each actor's skills, knowledge and experience will help in identifying what actors can bring to the project and what role suits them best in the group work.

4.1.2. Turn system understanding into actions

The other objective of system analysis is to find entry points into the system to generate the change you want to make. During system analysis, it is important to have in mind that the aim is to modify the system toward the expected objective. Thus, identification of the elements of the systems that may be modified to obtain expected results is important. **System analysis has to be combined with methods to think and plan the future transformation of the system.**

This requires methods to find the right points of entries, the relevant people to involve in the project and tools to understand the consequences of changes made in the system considered. For this, actors should be aware that change and innovation are dynamic processes that take time and necessitate adaptability. They should be **introduced to the mechanisms of change and innovation** whether to be able to accompany it correctly or to know how to proceed when they have a project requiring development of new technologies/technics. Thus, frameworks on how to think of these changes and their evolution, ability to identify the patterns, trajectories that are taking place, getting feedbacks and interpreting all these elements are important to adapt the strategy. Knowing how to identify the innovation arising from the projects is also important to improve it and share this innovation.

Building on system knowledge/system analysis and fundamental knowledge, transformative knowledge has also been recommended to make the diversification process more successful.

4.1.3. Communication skills

Personal interactions were mentioned in DiverIMPACTS Deliverable 1.1 as a major enabler for diversification. Involving actors in groups to tackle problems together were also greatly cited by interviewees to facilitate knowledge and experience exchange and system and problem perception confrontation.

Communication is key in fostering diversification as it allows actors to work together, share knowledge, point of views and advance toward a common goal. Therefore, it is necessary to develop communication skills: listening, summarizing, questioning, conflict resolution, consensus building, compromise building, multi-objectives approach, etc. Communication between actors that may not share the same professional culture and networking skills are highly useful when working with value chain actors.

Broker function, that would aim at connecting the right people together, identifying and amplifying ideas and knowledge from actors and ways to set things in motion toward action through the right means for the situation is highly relevant to help innovation and diversification.

4.1.4. Group facilitation skills

Skills for group facilitation (designing and leading meeting for groups of peers or multi-actors), compromise building, leadership and communication are recommended. Leaving space for each member of the group to share their knowledge and experiences, building consensus on the aim and ways of doing, organising to work together, identifying the incentives, i.e., what they can get from the exchange, for all actors to get involved in the project, could increase actors' motivation.

Organising meetings that are open for reflexion and contribution from all participants, enables the feeling of project ownership and involve participants more actively in the process. Also, identifying a common goal that suits the needs of all participants is an important aspect when starting a project. Finally, a reflexion must be performed in groups to divide and share tasks amongst participants, according to their preferences and experiences, their contributions and activities, for the group to succeed. This can lead to increased feeling of ownership of the project by the actors.

In Workload and Quality of Life Analysis (WP6), Respondents (farmers involved in CS) were asked to report if the time dedicated to different tasks had changed after diversifying their cropping system. The most significant increase in time allocated to different activities was engaging in knowledge exchange with other farmers and sharing knowledge speaking at events or on farm walks. This demonstrates that the majority of farmers surveyed increased their learning from other farmers making peer to peer support from other farmers who are diversifying cropping to be extremely valuable.

4.1.5. Other

Other important skills that have been mentioned and could contribute to diversification are skills required to develop new/ adapt existing machinery to the needs of the new crop.

4.2. Favourable attitudes

Complementarily to ways of doing, some attitudes are essential for fostering crop diversification. They could be defined as attitudes and personal skills.

4.2.1. Be adaptable and be able to adapt its attitude to the situation

During innovation and diversification processes, changes are occurring regularly and may not achieve the expected results. Thus, actors need to **be able to adapt their strategies, actions and more broadly their plans** regarding the evolution of the situation. Also, innovating is full of uncertainties; dealing with uncertainty and taking actions despite it, is necessary to move forward and improve the current system.

Actors, particularly advisors, should **be able to adapt their attitude** depending on the situation they face. For example, when dealing with group activities, they should **have an attitude that generates engagement** from participants, build trust and help in the initiation of actions from the group. Also, they should be **adopting an accompaniment attitude**; having a role where they listen and ask the right questions to the participant for them to properly express their views and goals and when necessary, change toward a more knowledgeable to share their expertise on the subject.

4.2.2. Be open-minded, curious and invested

Being open to new ideas, having curiosity to learn about new crops or cropping methods and aware of the changing technical, scientific and economic situations are an important attitude to be adopted by actors in order to stay experts on their field and knowing what happens beyond their field of expertise. Also, **reserving slots during working time to look for information, explore ideas and acquiring new knowledge** was mentioned as an important habit to adopt.

4.2.3. Take risks

Whoever the concerned actor is, adopting new crops/cropping system or create a new value chain entails taking risks and therefore assuming the potential negative consequences or failures. Indeed, given the lack of knowledge (dissemination) on diversification (under acquisition, incomplete, evolving), risk of yield variability and insecurity of minor crops (in terms of market but also due to technological issues), many stakeholders hesitate to invest in the diversification of crops. Thus, taking the risk, being a pioneer is a sought attitude necessary to acquire more references on a crop, its production techniques, processing, marketing, etc.

It is also difficult for advisors who are accustomed to providing advice on tried and tested techniques or products, to advise farmers on 'new' techniques whose results are variable or not guaranteed.

To overcome this risk, a farmer or an advisor needs to be confident in his peers, both in their individual and group works. The existence of a safety net in case of mistakes and the reinsurance of other actors can also help to adopt crop diversification practices.

4.2.4. Act!

“Think where you want to be and how you want to get there and then turn it into action” (DiverIMPACTS researcher).

All work package leaders mentioned the necessity for actors to take actions and experiment at their own scale (e.g., field level). Actors must realise that they have the possibility to improve their current system and that it is not always at other levels of the value chain that the barrier exists. **Generating change starts by doing and experimenting.** For change to happen, one should not depend on others, but be the pioneer and start experimenting. Also, they should experiment and do things despite the judgements that may arise from their social environment.

4.2.5. Work collectively

Actors should try to work collectively, to share knowledge, information, advices, points of views, to understand the context and the problem at stake.

4.3. Knowledge

Knowledge of crop diversification are ever evolving and disseminating them through training and formal education can help in the increased adoption/acceptance by actors. Having basic general knowledge to build on and the skills and attitudes to keep up to date with new practices, new crops and approaches for crop diversification are an important aspect for meeting actor's needs.

4.3.1. Type of knowledge

4.3.1.1. Promote multi-disciplinarity

Basic knowledge on agronomy, ecology, economy, sociology, policy making, governance mechanisms, marketing, accounting and sustainability are necessary for all actors in order to be able to understand the context in which they are working and effectively communicate with each other on the various aspects of the problems they face. Also, knowledge of the actors and institutions of AKIS are useful to identify the type of actors to involve and the roles of institutions present in the territory.

All knowledge mentioned above aim at enabling actors to have a **global understanding of their context**, know the **actors and institutions they may mobilise** and establish common ground to **communicate with different experts**. Also, mastering these types of knowledge is important for actors' credibility and legitimacy.

4.3.1.2. Contextualized knowledge

What is noticed through CS observation is that farmers bring together multiple knowledge, multiple actors of the socio-economic environment and different types of tests at the farm in order to produce contextualized references necessary for action. Indeed, the exclusive focus on the technological or knowledge is insufficient because crop diversification lock-in are not purely technical. By linking fundamental and technical learnings, actors could understand the mechanisms underlying potential benefits and risks for the conception and management of diversified cropping systems.

4.3.2. Field & Crop specific knowledge

4.3.2.1. Crop diversification strategies and their benefits

First, spreading awareness on the impacts of simplified systems and associated practices (Morel et al. 2020) as well as benefits of diversification to address these impacts are crucial.

It was pointed out that it is important to **present and promote crop diversification as a means to overcome problems associated with low diversity cropping systems** such as declining soil health and increased susceptibility to weeds, diseases and pests. For example, when weeds are difficult to control in maize grown within short rotations, farmers or advisors should keep in mind that strategies of crop diversification are options to reduce weed pressure. Also, being aware of the benefits of diversification and implementing it may be a pro-active approach to avoid problems associated with simplified cropping systems. Indeed, through DiverIMPACTS activities, it was observed that diversification of cropping systems by farmers was mainly driven by problems encountered in their simplified cropping systems, less often motivated by an opportunity (e.g., subsidies, market availabilities or growing demand from consumer).

Once the benefits of cropping system diversification are identified, actors should be aware of the various available crop diversification strategies, e.g., increase rotation duration, intercropping or/and multiple cropping. **Knowledge on temporal and spatial diversification strategies were incomplete amongst actors** and in cropping system diversification experiment design. Furthermore, there seems to a lack of **knowledge on how to combine these different diversification strategies** (e.g., how to combine crops in intercropping or where to insert a specific crop in the rotation). Actors were asking for technical information on ways to implement these strategies and which decisions rules to apply.

In addition, actors need to be conscious that **diversification is a dynamic process**, which takes time and that the benefits may not be visible in the first years of diversification. There are still questions on how to evaluate the diversification strategies used to tune them more precisely to their cropping system and how to characterise the services obtained from diversification.

Spreading awareness of the challenges of the first years of a crop introduction within a system and develop methodologies associated with this specific period for experimentation, adaptation of foreign references and more generally guidelines on how to proceed may be of interest.

4.3.2.2. Pre-crop effect

DiverIMPACTS contributions highlighted a lack of **knowledge on pre-crop/carry over effects**. Having more information on the effects of crops on each other would make it easier to identify the benefits of introducing certain crops in the cropping system for the following crops. It was observed that it was rather rare that farmers diversified their systems with pre-crop effect as an objective (except for organic farmers looking for nitrogen). It is only after the introduction of the new crop that they observe the impact on the following crops. Nevertheless, farmers may look for the “rotation effect” when diversifying, regardless of the crop introduced.

4.3.2.3. Move past the rotation concept

Crop rotation is a very useful scientific concept. However, in practice it may not be so easy to implement and may constrain actors in a rigid framework. Indeed, rotation implies a rather stable sequence of crops that comes back in the field regularly. It may not leave room for experimentations and adaptation to opportunities or hazards.

Thinking in terms of crop sequence patterns by considering field history allows farmers to adapt and experiment and this may provide the necessary flexibility to address emergent problems (e.g., resistant pests or weeds) through diversification before they become too problematic. **Moving beyond 'strict' rotation, toward a dynamic cropping system planning and adaptive management** may also offer the adaptability necessary to modify cropping sequence, combining management constraints, agronomic management and economic opportunities. This argument comes from the observation that farmers who regularly experiment new crops tend to think of crop sequences instead of rotation, while other farmers tend to experiment less and often adopt the same cropping practice.

4.3.3. For different scales, both Field and Value chain/territory

4.3.3.1. Systems analysis

“It is not possible to develop a strategy independently from the systems in which this strategy is integrated” (DiverIMPACTS researcher).

Taking into account the different scales of the systems (e.g., cropping systems, value chain, territory), in which the actions have to be implemented, has been unanimously identified by interviewees as necessary knowledge for all actors. Building on the fundamental knowledge mentioned earlier in this document, **system analysis** should be widely used to understand the functioning and the impact of modification of some component of such system. Indeed, lock-ins hindering cropping systems diversification may be at other systems scales.

At field scale, after identifying that diversification of cropping system and pre-crop effects may be valuable management options to improve performances of the system, system thinking has to be mastered to properly piece together a long-term management of the cropping system. This requires farmers and advisors to consider the system as a whole rather than planning and advising crop by crop. It has been identified that farmers acquire knowledge on their system through experience rather than from advisors or other partners. Advisors often provide advice to actors on specific crops and may not have the knowledge for sound system analysis, to provide systemic management advices.

Then, actors should be able to analyse their systems at different scales. Indeed, an agronomic problem may be solved through careful cropping system diversification but the choice of the crop to use for diversification may greatly be influenced by the farming system constraints (e.g., bio-physical, social, economic) or territory context (e.g., storage facilities, transformation industries). Conversely, a manufacturer may encounter problems that could be solved by mobilising other scales of the system. **Bringing awareness to the actors on the importance of looking at different scales of the system and how they may interact** should help identify barriers and entry points to solve or overcome the barriers to cropping system diversification.

Furthermore, actors' **understanding of their systems through different points of view and different scales** should contribute to a better system understanding and ease the identification of the problems and potential solutions. However, this necessitates knowledge on how to gather all the elements constituting the context/situation (e.g., actors, institutions, economy, ecology) and understand how they interact with each other. This exercise of system analysis at different scales and from different points of views should aim at seeing the problem from outside of our usual system limitations (e.g.,

for a farmer seeing its system from the territory point of view rather than only at field or farm scale; for a manufacturer, looking at territory level rather than only value chain). This should help to identify new components that can be mobilised to solve the issue. The aim being to understand the system they work with, the context in which it is integrated and how all the components of the given system interact and function together, rather than focussing on a precise element of the system.

Interviewees insisted on the social component of the systems. Looking at the bigger picture, to see how the system interacts with the territory and how it may affect it, as well as clearly identifying what can be done at system scale to change toward the common goal is a way to engage people. Also, during system analysis, it was suggested to identify the relevant social resources and interactions that can be used.

4.3.3.2. Impact on management and organisation

Our results highlighted the lack of knowledge of the impact of diversification on management aspects of the systems. Such knowledge lacks are diverse with needs on mid-term economic impact, impact on workload and work organisation, trade-offs and compromises to make between different aspects of the system, how to deal with many different crops, small volumes, diversity of markets, logistic issues...

4.4. Conclusion

Skills, attitudes and knowledge to accompany crop diversification are diverse and numerous to master and to mobilize with agility. This suggests to discontinue the prescriptive way of doing and training and shift to continuous learning/accompaniment. Moreover, ways of training and teaching have to evolve to increase awareness on multi-actor and multi-discipline approaches.

5. DiverIMPACTS resources

We list below resources from the project DiverIMPACTS that should be used for training and education contents. Many of these resources have not been produced as training materials but the actors can take over these contents for improving their knowledge and skills or to adapt them as training materials.

5.1. Knowledge and tools

5.1.1. Models & Indicators

Tools can be used in two ways to help in cropping system diversification. First of all, they can assist in system characterisation and analysis, providing indicators to base their decision on. In addition, they can be used to highlight the importance of a multi-performance approach, considering all dimensions of sustainability (agronomical, ecological and economical) and the existence of benefits and drawbacks in diversifying a system and the trade-offs that it may imply. In DiverIMPACTS, several models were developed, adapted or improved for different system scales, from field to territory:

SMART diversification tool at the farm and cropping system, MAELIA at the territory scale. These tools require training and time to use them and might not be accessible to everyone; they should be used with care for decision making purposes. Nonetheless, they can also be used as educational resources and serve several purposes: they provide examples of the impact on how changes may affect the system considered. Using such tools in formal education/trainings creates awareness that such resources exist and actors can later look for the tool best suited for their needs. Based on real life situations, the use of tools for illustration of diversification benefits and drawbacks on several aspects of the system can be a powerful support for reflection.

Actors asked for indicators, which are easy to use to assess the impact of diversification on their systems, and suggested the creation of an app for data collection and indicator calculation. A list of indicators was provided by DiverIMPACTS WP4.

A crop diversity index was also created to estimate the ecosystem services expected from a crop sequence. Also, multicriteria assessment tools (i.e., MAELIA (<http://maelia-platform.inra.fr/>) and SMART (<https://www.fibl.org/en/themes/smart-en/smart-details-en.html>)) were adapted to better consider diversification benefits and drawbacks at cropping system, farm and territory scales. Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) protocols have been also developed to take better account of the effects of diversification with addition of biodiversity-related indicators and use of several functional units.

5.1.2. Tools for system analysis/diagnosis

DiverIMPACTS activities were organised around the accompaniment of diversification case studies. At the beginning of the project, co-innovation workshops were organised to help actors of the different case studies to reflect on their problems and systems. During these workshops, numerous activities were aimed at understanding the social context and identification of the most important actors to involve in the case studies. To this end, several facilitation methods and tools were tested with actors and will be made available to the public. **Stakeholder analysis** and **causal analysis** methods are two of them. A practical guide for these methods is being drafted in French.

5.1.3. Practice abstracts

Technical resources were required by actors to facilitate the decision-making process, in particular to better understand diversification strategies and their applications. Thus, actors suggested investing in the translation of on-farm and on-station experimental results into relevant decision-making documents that can be reused for action in other places/contexts. They also suggested the redaction of **Practice Abstracts (PA)** at regional scale with reference to experimental stations or farms to visit or to contact for further information. DiverIMPACTS produced **Practice Abstracts (PA)** to provide examples and explanations on diversification practices and strategies. Finally, methodology guides for on-farm experimentation were suggested as valuable resource to help diversification and innovation processes.

Practice abstracts could also cover the socio-technical context of a diversification strategy. For instance, a practice abstract will be published to present a tool for fair price which give a reference frame and could help actors to define a fair price for diversification crops. A report from WP5 (under

realization) will also be published with suggestions on how to overcome barriers to diversification for different actors.

5.1.4. ToolBox for crop diversification

One of the identified skills necessary to foster crop diversification is to search and contextualise knowledge for action. This could equip actors to choose the right resource among possibilities for the right context and replace the outputs of the tool in the farmer's reflexion process.

The Toolbox for Crop Diversification was created to help a large scope of actors (e.g., farmers, advisors, actors of value chain, innovation brokers) in the identification of the relevant resources to foster crop diversification according to their project. This Toolbox which is available on the DiverIMPACTS website for public use, covers a wide range of activities and strategies linked to crop diversification (i.e., assessment, consultation of technical references, diagnosis, initiation of partnerships, decision support, examples and inspirational documents).

5.2. “Inspirational documents”

Many contributors to this work brought out the fact that documented examples of diversification experiences and trajectories would be really useful to get inspiration from and to realise or to understand the dynamic nature of such project.

First of all, stories to highlight the challenges generated by simplified systems may help bring awareness to and engagement from actors to act toward diversification, especially if they can identify how such challenge may affect them. This should be accompanied by a clear narrative on why and how to diversify in order to present diversification as part of the solutions.

Documentation and sharing of diversification trajectories in different contexts can constitute an important source of knowledge, examples and inspiration for anyone involved in diversification projects. Indeed, providing stories from different trajectories of change with rationale behind decisions, the actors involved (when, why, how), technologies mobilised over time and elements of context will hopefully help actors recognise similarities with their situations and inspire them for their project.

Such documented trajectories may have multiple purposes: provide example of diversification strategies and technologies, highlight the dynamic nature of diversification process, emphasize the diversity of solutions in multiple contexts, bring to light the actors' roles in the process and initiate to the identification of the stakes, the patterns of change and innovation processes, and help in identification of opportunities.

DiverIMPACTS project provided such examples through practice abstracts redaction, trajectories documentation of diversification initiatives at different scales (available on DiverIMPACTS website: <https://www.diverimpacts.net/success-stories.html>) along with a database of diversification initiatives in Europe (Drexler, 2018).

5.3. Inspirational examples of animation and information sharing from DiverIMPACTS

5.3.1. Work in groups and Co-innovation workshops

“We had regular meetings, where everyone presented their new experiences and where the presentation in the project reports were discussed. Finished reports were also presented and discussed. That was very well done. It was fun to do there. I think that has contributed a lot to the success.” (Quote from an actor involved in a diversification project).

Working in groups was perceived as a factor of success for implementation of crop diversification in the DiverIMPACTS project. These groups consist of peers or different stakeholders involved in the value chain or any actor interested in the process.

In DiverIMPACTS, case studies were composed of several actors that had a common goal, they were organised in clusters of case studies to facilitate information and resource exchange across Europe. This helped in sharing understanding and experiences on comparable problems from different points of view because of the different contexts they were located in. Also, working in clusters were appreciated by actors involved in the case studies as it provided a close and effective networking opportunities.

One important component for actors in case studies is to improve their skills and attitudes is to get and give feedbacks on skills and attitudes. However, giving feedbacks may be a delicate exercise and needs clear rules on how to give them and requires practice. Thus, in both formal education and training sessions, providing feedbacks and receiving them has to be encouraged to all actors to be able to reflect on their skills and attitudes and how to improve them. Dedicating specific time in the meeting schedule to give feedback has been done in DiverIMPACTS case studies meeting and was well received by participants. That was one of the tasks of the monitor of case study. In addition to rules on how to give feedbacks, building trust between group members and daring to give feedbacks are two important components which can help to increase success in activities.

Finally, in DiverIMPACTS case studies supporting, importance was given to making sure that stakeholders were on board with the objectives of the project and were motivated enough to act, with reasonable goals, before starting any actions. The case studies emphasised the importance of stakeholder engagement in the project.

5.3.2. Good practices for sharing results

As mentioned by WP2 team, sharing knowledge is an important part of CS activities. Due to COVID-19 outbreak, many on-site meetings and workshops, face-to-face interviews and field days have been replaced by virtual meetings during 2020-21. DiverIMPACTS partners found new ways to connect with actors in the pandemic. WP2 and WP7 teams provided accompaniment such as a webinar on exchange on online meetings.

5.3.3. Exchange platforms

Virtual places to meet peers, exchange knowledge, debate, share data, link different actors already exist at country levels. The creation of such platform dedicated to cropping system diversification may be necessary and it might be beneficial to implement a website referencing all platforms at European level so that actors may look for information and contacts for their project in other countries. Encouraging all actors and students to participate in these platforms to learn and share resources is also advisable. However, it requires critical information analysis to only use information that is relevant. On-line courses on diversification can also contribute to awareness on these strategies. Within DiverIMPACTS project, a set of webinars and have been organised (starting from February 2019). They were dedicated to specific topics and results presentations or more dedicated to exchanging between partners on a specific topic.

5.3.4. Leaders/monitors

Each case study of DiverIMPACTS project had a tandem composed of a leader and a monitor who works closely together in organising multi-actor activities in relation to the case study objectives. To have a team with complementary roles and skills supports the quality of the interventions in the case study. They were trained in group facilitation and progress assessment methods. Impact of such training and organisation is being monitored through the WP2 activities.

5.3.5. Training sessions and MSc Course materials

Four training sessions held between January and May 2021 were organised by BIONEXT, LWK, APCA / APCA and APCA (MS22). Due to COVID-19 outbreak, only one session out of four could be organised physically, the rest were remote events. The online sessions were addressed to a large audience, farmers, advisors but also actors of the socio-technic context. They covered different technical aspects of crop diversification: strip-cropping, cover-crops, inter-cropping and insertion of legumes in the rotation, but also impacts on value chains. These webinars are good as first introductions but not sufficient for really changing practices with farmers. Nevertheless, they allowed sharing a common framework and knowledge base between different actors (farmers, advisors, value chain actors...).

Different resources from DiverIMPACTS have been used in the different sessions such as testimonials from case studies leaders or monitors (WP2, WP4), presentation of results from field experiments (WP3), presentation of resources from DiverIMPACTS (WP2, WP4, WP6, WP7).

Such training sessions can be used outside the project, and can especially set an example of vocational trainings that need to be organised in the future to set-up knowledge on cropping system diversification.

Likewise, a MSc course module will be developed based on contents from the project (i.e., CSs examples, results from WP3/4/5)

6. Identified needs in knowledge, skills and attitudes; associated recommendations in education and training strategy and usable resources from DiverIMPACTS project

The table below (Table 2) figures the different needs in knowledge, skills and attitudes and proposes for each of them some practical recommendations for training and education sectors. Some usable examples of resources are also added to illustrate the recommendations.

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Table 2 Summary table of the identified needs in knowledge, skills and attitudes; associated recommendations in education and training strategy and usable resources from DiverIMPACTS project

Category	Identified need/gap to fill	Associated recommendation in training and education strategy	Usable resources provided by DiverIMPACTS
Skills	On-farm experimentation.	Introduce training (vocational & formal education) on experimentation on-farm (e.g., principle, methods) different from conventional experimentation led by professionals in experimentation (e.g., researchers, technical farms) as the aim and the pilot of these two types of experimentation are different.	Practice abstracts on Field experiments and Case studies demonstrations.
	Analysis and diagnostics skills.	Systematically link fundamental knowledge to technical and empirical ones to contribute to this diagnostic and understanding of diversification crop success and failure and to contextualise knowledge for action.	Stakeholder analysis and causal analysis methods (WP2) available in the frame of a methodological guide.
	Working in network.	Vocational training: organise training sessions for farmers on the existing technological tools, professional websites, forums, allowing them to be autonomous in searching information and being connected to each-other.	online seminar (March 02, 2021) “Exchanging experiences managing online and online/on-site events”_was dedicated to exchanging with others about experiences hosting such events.
	Ability to task a technological watch.	Formal higher education: even if young generations regularly use internet, they lack the rules and good	Toolbox for crop diversification: this tool allows identifying

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		practices to have an efficient watch. Thus, there is need to democratize and generalize courses on web search and watch. Indeed, mainly courses on literature monitoring are displayed for students.	resources on crop diversification regarding different criteria chosen by the end-user. It could be a first step for technological watch.
	General communication and animation skills (group facilitation, listening, summarizing, questioning, conflict resolution, consensus building, multi-objectives approach.	Skills needed for farmers but mainly for advisors that would switch to a broker function: Vocational training: afford training on accompaniment and animation tools and skills to all advisors (not only those who are in charge of group animation). Formal higher education: systematize courses on animation/communication/working in multi-cultural and multi-disciplinary environment in order to heighten awareness of future farmers/technicians to work in a multi-scale and multi-disciplinary environment.	Co-innovation Course programme established Deliverable 2.1: Description of the co-innovation training within DiverIMPACTS. How to ensure demonstration events are successful for knowledge exchange: practice abstract : Skills training in knowledge exchange and event coordination improves inter-sector communication. This can enhance the quality and quantity of research dissemination while influencing on-farm practices.
	Ability to adapt/invent machinery adapted to minor crops.		A report with “guidelines for machinery requirements enabling crop diversification at the

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			different levels of supply chain” is under realization and practice abstract is planned to present the main outcomes.
Attitudes	Adaptability/open-mindedness, curiosity.	No specific training is indicated to develop these needed attitudes but they should derive automatically when actors attain the knowledge and skills identified such as: On-farm experimentation Capacity to identify and challenge the appropriate stakeholders.	
	Ability to manage uncertainty and risky decisions.	Having other guaranties such as minimum income when trying a new/risky crop that may fail for a farmer.	
Knowledge	Promote multi-disciplinarity.	Train (or at least sensitize) all involved actors to multi-scale and multi-discipline approaches. This is already initiated in many higher education programs. We recommend to enlarge to technical/professional education programs which are today very discipline-focused (e.g., animal production, crop production, machinery, agricultural business management). This will allow to	Co-innovation Course programme established in Deliverable 2.1 : Description of the co-innovation training within DiverIMPACTS. Success and failure factors of European diversification experiences: different outputs

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		<p>Train advisors/counsellors capable to converse with different stakeholders and at many scales of the value chain</p> <p>Train farmers able to see the problem from outside of their usual system limitations (usually field or farm scale)</p>	<p>from DiverIMPACTS have described and precised these factors (WP1, WP5) at different scales.</p>
	<p>Field and crop specific knowledge linked to crop diversification, pre-crop effect, move past the rotation concept.</p>	<p>Increase awareness on diversification options and benefits: In both vocational & formal education: need to present and identify diversification of cropping system as a mean to overcome problems associated with low diversity cropping systems such as soil fertility decrease or weed and pest management. This is already the case in many programs but we need to insist and generalize this point → introduce systematic courses on crop diversification.</p>	<p>Diversity index developed in the project (WP4) to know the ecosystem services obtained from increasing length of the cropping sequence.</p> <p>Set of practice abstracts on diversification options, success stories and set of webinars.</p> <p>Training sessions organized in 2021 on different topics: strip, cropping, cover-crops, legumes... (replays available).</p>
		<p>Introduce and insist on the concept of crop sequence rather than crop rotation that is much more rigid and less adapted to crop diversification and on-farm experimentation.</p>	
	<p>Knowledge at different scales</p>	<p>Introduce system analysis concept and tools in vocational and professional education which allow:</p> <p>advisors to use the appropriate methods, tools and indicators and position their reflexion at the right frame of</p>	<p>Stakeholder analysis and causal analysis methods.</p> <p>List of the identified criteria and indicators to evaluate crop diversification sustainability and</p>

		<p>work (larger than the crop/field scale) allowing them to tackle diversification issues and help farmers.</p> <p>Make farmers identify barriers and entry points to solve or overcome the barriers to cropping system diversification.</p>	<p>performance: DiverIMPACTS developed an adapted analytical framework to evaluate crop diversification sustainability and performance. The final list of the identified criteria and the related indicators is composed of 19 criteria and 29 performance indicators.</p> <p>Indicator “Crop Diversity Index »</p> <p>Indicator « Short food supply chain and local distribution (PSC) »</p> <p>MAELIA at territory scale</p> <p>SMART diversification tool at cropping system scale</p> <p>Toolbox for crop diversification</p> <p>Some of these tools could be used as training materials with groups of students for example</p>
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7. Conclusion

Training and formal education should ensure that skills and attitudes described above are apprehended by actors. Indeed, mastering these skills takes time and practice but using them early in the career helps to master them faster. Also, adaptability, curiosity, open-mindedness, networking, communication skills allow the actors to increase their knowledge on a subject through various channels. In addition, ensuring that actors have at least a basic understanding of agronomy and other fundamental knowledge is important for them to be able to later look into more details on the specific subject they are working on.

To assist in the diversification process and more broadly on innovation, proposing only trainings and formal education activities on knowledge, whether they are fundamental or technical, is not enough. Skills and attitudes, have a great importance in facilitating relations between actors, groups facilitation, and thus knowledge exchange and success of diversification initiative.

One of the key aspects is to make sure that actors are aware of the existing knowledge sources, the skills that may be need and how to develop them and of the importance of attitudes. Once actors know about all those elements, they can deepen their understanding and mastery of the topics and skills they find most useful to their activities.

Building knowledge, skills and improving attitudes has to be part of a position related to diversification, at large. There are many ways to achieve this process. Amongst them are master classes and summer schools, visits, at other levels of the value chain, of peers in other regions or countries, training session, seminars, webinars, on-farm experiments, working on real-life situations and many others. An important aspect may be to combine means of knowledge, skill and attitudes improvement and dedicate time for it. Professionals should have time in their schedule to search for information and technical watch, to keep their knowledge up to date and explore new research/technology topics. Encouraging interpersonal information exchange through platforms, networking events, seminaries.

All actors involve in agriculture should at least be initiated to the knowledge necessary for crop diversification, so they are aware of these solutions and can look for more information if they are interested in. However, depending on their curriculum, they may not need the same level of detail in their formation. In depth exploration of knowledge and skills, should be chosen in relation to functions actors (will) have in the diversification projects.

During formal education, knowledge and skills can be acquired through many forms that are already used in programs. However, emphasizing experience-based learning, with real-life situations and interaction with actors should help develop knowledge and practice skills presented in this document. Furthermore, exchanges or experiences in very different contexts (region or countries) with activities requiring the student to analyse the context and system he is working on is advisable.

In both formal education and professional training, working with complementary resources with classes/training sessions, personal search for information, videos, exchange platforms, professional travels to other regions, peers meeting and debates, on-site experiments should be advised.

Through the case studies, DiverIMPACTS tested and used many of the skills and attitudes as well as the resources and methodology mentioned in this document, to accompany these diversification

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projects. Actors involved in these projects gained skills and knowledge and may have adopted changes in their attitudes.

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Other DiverIMPACTS deliverables used in this report

Deliverable 1.1 Typology of diversification experiences with description of driving factors to support crop diversification (31/05/2018)

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Deliverable 1.3 - Crop diversification experiences across Europe - In depth analysis of crop diversification experience types: relative importance of key factors (barriers, drivers, lock-ins, etc.) and description of the pathways to crop diversification

Deliverable 2.3 - Mid-term CSs' evolutions in terms of quantitative and qualitative indicators

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Deliverable 6.3 Needs for training and advisory as well as for formal education (28/05/2020)

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Supplementary material 1 Interview guide for review of needs

The purpose is to perform semi-structured interviews in order to leave large answer possibilities for the interviewee. By this way, they can express ideas, skills, or even recommendation we didn't expected.

Interviews will take maximum 1h30, this guide have to allow to quickly get at the heart of the matter

Presentation, experience

Briefly, what are your experiences about crop diversification?

Briefly, what are your experiences about teaching, training, advising (on diversification or not)?

What audience? Students, apprentices, farmers, advisors, ...

What was your role, attitude? Observer, animator, advisor, teacher, facilitator, ...

Have you ever encountered specific problems or difficulties when you are working on crop diversification, or on a specific minor crop? If yes, which ones?

If you used to deal with this subject, which methods and knowledges do you prefer?

Key skills identification

The purpose is to bring out skills that should be developed by farmers and teacher, advisors, animator, ... Theses ones can be already worked and approached in existed formations, or not.

We want identify the type of skills and where they should be developed: by which actors and through which relationships?

Does some knowledge sound essential, primordial to get or give to work on diversification? Prerequisite?

Fundamental or technical

Implication of different scientific disciplines

On which object of the agroecosystem? Agronomic, economic, management, post-harvest activities, mechanic, market, ...

On which scale of the supply chain?

Which skills are important to manipulate diverse knowledge?

Scientific / empirical, generic / contextualised or located

How combine it and hybridize knowledge

How articulate it at a given situation, problematic experience: use of a practical case?

Multidisciplinary

How to make (raise) actors' awareness of the multiple sources and channels of knowledge?

How to adopt a facilitator attitude, coach, animator instead of a prescriptive attitude?

Create a space and conditions for reflexivity

Don't be prescriptive anymore

How to take account of the farmer trajectory, in order to understand which kind of pathway he is building?

It seems very important to work on different scale at the same time, or at least to take account of these different scales (from field to the value chain). What skills can allow this consideration?

What skill are useful or necessary to elaborate multi-actor partnerships?

Description of the existing systems and trainings

National or regional state of overview

In the "sector" of the interviewee: initial formation, professional formation, for farmers, advisors, groups ...

Make an overview of the configuration of the different organisations and stakeholders (place in the AKIS).

Detail description of one or two training session

With the interviewee, choose a training session or a support method (network, working group, ...) according to these two criteria:

The method must be different to these ones we already have explain in the precedent interviews, in order to inventory the larger range of different training session as possible.

The method or training session present, according to the interviewee, a strong potential to support crop diversification and to develop skills we've talk before.

It's important to deal with the content (prerequisite, goals) and the form, tools.

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Link the training session with few skills we've talk before.

Is there any barriers or obstacles to develop some skills? Take precise example. If yes, how get around the problem?

Take one or two key concepts previously discussed (ex: intermediation, knowledge hybridization, knowledge transfer, ...), and ask what skills could be developed to aim these concepts.

In what extent the activities, lessons, exercises of this training session can be transposed in another training session or another education course? Perform with other actors, from educational courses to professional training (vice versa).

Prospective: idea of recommendations?

According to the interviewee and the remaining time, ask: based on your experience and your works, do you have ideas of recommendations that could be done to support a specific skill?

Choose one or two skills, for each:

What pedagogical goals have to be defined to develop this skill?

What actors must be concern by this skill (skill scope)?

What necessary conditions must be present or establish to develop this skill?

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Supplementary material 2 List of interviews for review of needs

Sophie DUHAMEL	RESOLIA (APCA) - FR
Marianne LE BAIL	AgroParisTech - FR
Adrien Guichaoua	ACTA / AKIS, Horizon Bio2020 (FR - UE)
Margot Leclère	INRAE, Wageningen, Arvalis / Co-leader du cluster 3 "Crop Diversification in systems from Western Europe" (FR-NL)
Lieven Delanote	Inagro (BE)
Benjamin Fouilly	APCA - DEPHY (FR)
Katie Bliss	ORC (EN)
James Maher	TEAGASC - curriculum development in contact with crops teachers (IR)
Brüno Haller	EUFRAS - HAFL - Responsable du groupe de formation et conseil (CH)
Pablo Asensio	EUFRAS - Ministère de l'Agriculture de Bavière, centre de formation FÜAK (DE)

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Supplementary material 3 List of interviews within the project

WP	WP title	Name of the interviewee(s)
WP1	Identification of success and failure factors of crop diversification across Europe	Frédéric Vanwindekens (CRA-W)
WP2	Promoting crop diversification in case studies through actor-oriented research	Walter Rossing (WUR) Yvonne CUIJPERS (WUR)
WP3	Quantification of the benefits from diversified cropping systems through field experiments	Guenaelle Hellou (ESA)
WP4	Sustainability assessment of crop diversification at farm, value chain and territory levels	Frédérique Angevin (INRAe) Eva Revoyron (AgroParisTech)
WP5	From lock-ins to innovations and value chain redesign	Clémentine Antier (UCL) Stephan Marette (INRAe)